

La protein binding to telomerase RNA supports an evolutionary relationship between plant and ciliate telomerase pathways

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Abstract

The *Arabidopsis thaliana* La1 (AtLa1) protein is a member of the genuine La family of RNA biogenesis proteins, which are structurally similar to the La-related protein 7 (LARP7) family. LARP7 proteins participate in the biogenesis of the telomerase ribonucleoprotein complex in model systems, but are absent in plants. We show that AtLa1 binds to telomerase RNA in a manner reminiscent of the *Tetrahymena* LARP7 protein p65. Classical *in vitro* methods and microscale thermophoresis (MST) were used to specify the molecular structures involved in this multi-surface interaction. AtLa1 also enhances the binding of TR to the telomerase reverse transcriptase RNA binding domain. We therefore propose that biogenesis of telomerase RNA in plants and ciliates is achieved by a similar pathway, differing in the employment of genuine La or LARP7-like proteins, respectively. We also report that the domain of unknown function (DUF3223, DeCL) found in the AtLa1 protein binding partner, Domino, is an RNA binding domain with modest TR-binding capacity. This domain is also found in plant and ciliate proteins, including plant polymerases IV/V and the *Tetrahymena* La protein Mlp1. Together, these suggest that RNA biogenesis pathways in plants and ciliates have a conserved evolutionary relationship, with parallels between their La proteins.

Graphical abstract

Introduction

The RNA-binding La protein family emerged during the early evolution of eukaryotes, characterized by an La-motif and a downstream RNA-recognition motif (RRM), which together form an La module (LaM, Fig. 1A) [1–6]. Substrate recognition of La proteins in most species also involves a variant RRM domain close to the C-terminus [2]. The La-motif is

sensitive to the 3' trailer of RNA, binding UUU-3'OH (poly-U) with high affinity and stability [5–8], whereas RRM domain(s) are responsible for broader substrate specificity [9–11]. Genuine La proteins typically bind RNA shortly after transcription by polymerase III, often acting as chaperones or regulators of RNA folding [1]. Members of the La-related protein (LARP) superfamily are continuing to be characterized and

Received: April 25, 2025. Revised: February 18, 2026. Accepted: February 20, 2026

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grouped into subfamilies based on variations in structure and biological roles [2]. These include nuclear LARPs that function in processing and maturation of precursor tRNA, spliceosomal and other snRNA transcripts, and cytoplasmic LARPs involved in messenger RNA (mRNA) metabolism and translation [12, 13]. Recent work by Kao *et al.* 2024 [14] linked nuclear LARP proteins, namely LARP7 and LARP3 (a genuine La protein in humans), to sequential processing of human telomerase RNA precursors, using an *in vitro* approach. Searches of the genome of the model land plant *Arabidopsis thaliana* (At) identified eight putative La or LARP proteins [15]. Of these, sequence information suggests that two are genuine La proteins, one of which (termed AtLa1, Fig. 1A) can rescue non-coding RNA biogenesis functions in yeast missing their native genuine La protein, which is not the case for the AtLa2 protein [15]. AtLa1 also binds pre-tRNA *via* the UUU-3'OH (poly-U) tails common to polymerase III transcripts, is located in the nucleus, and is essential for embryogenesis [15]. Intriguingly, the same AtLa1 protein was identified among the top co-purified proteins interacting with At telomerase reverse transcriptase (TERT) in pulldown experiments [16]. However, there is no direct AtLa1 protein–protein interaction with AtTERT [17]. Telomerase is a ribonucleoprotein complex responsible for synthesizing short repetitive DNA sequences at 3' ends of linear chromosomes, providing ablative protection against the end replication problem in cells where it is active [18]. The catalytic core of all known telomerases consists of the protein subunit TERT and a non-coding RNA, termed telomerase RNA (TR) [19, 20]; see [21] for review. Despite high evolutionary variability [22], TRs have conserved structural features, namely the template region and a pseudoknot [23, 24]; often, they also feature one or more stem-loop arms, which serve as a flexible scaffold for assembly of the telomerase RNP complex [21, 24].

Before its role in telomerase was identified, AtTR was termed ATR8 and investigated for its role in hypoxia responses [25]. AtTR is a polymerase III transcript (see [21] for review), and although there is some question of where exactly the 3' end terminates [20, 25], a short poly-U tail is tolerated for reconstitution of telomerase activity *in vitro* [19, 20, 26]. In eukaryotes, it is typical for the *in vivo* telomerase complex to interact with multiple accessory proteins responsible for its biosynthesis and regulation (reviewed in [27, 28]). Mature, catalytically active complexes feature species-specific proteins with both parallels and differences between organisms [29, 30], reviewed in [31]. Proteins from the LARP7 family are one such conserved group, proposed to have a role in TR biogenesis and as subunits of the active telomerase complex, namely p65 and p43 in Alveolates *Tetrahymena* and *Euplotes* [8, 32], respectively, and Pof8 (Lar7) in *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* [33–35] (Fig. 1A). Telomeres progressively shorten when human LARP7 is absent [36], and this protein can counterbalance LARP3 in the processing of immature forms of human TR [14] after its transcription from the polymerase II promoter. Despite this, LARP7 is not present in active human telomerase, with its role seemingly replaced by histones H2A and H2B [30]. LARP7 proteins have a domain structure similar to that of genuine La proteins (Fig. 1A). One difference is that their RRM2 domain, termed an extended helical RRM (xRRM), has an additional helix and conserved features that allow for a variant mode of RNA binding to specific patterns of ss- and dsRNA. Examples of this are Pof8 binding to the telomerase RNA subunit in *S. pombe* [35] and

Tetrahymena p65 binding to its respective TR [11]. Curiously, plants lack an obvious LARP7 protein, although some plants, including At, have two genuine La proteins [2, 15]. AtLa1 also fulfils expected genuine La functions, e.g. pre-tRNA and snoRNA binding [15, 37], and is able to functionally compensate for loss of budding yeast homolog Lhp1p *in vivo*, unlike the AtLa2 protein [15]. It is therefore plausible that the co-purification of AtLa1 observed in a TAP/MS study [16] may be caused by its interaction with AtTR and/or with other co-purified telomerase partners.

AtLa1 has a single known protein–protein interaction with Domino [17, 38], a plant-specific protein of unknown function that is located in the nucleus, is essential for embryogenesis [39], and co-purifies and interacts with AtTERT [16, 17]. Intriguingly, the domain of unknown function (DUF3223, aka DeCL) in Domino is also found in the genuine La proteins of Alveolates [2, 40] (Fig. 1A), as well as being present in the C-terminus of plant-specific AtPolymerase IV and V [41, 42], and defective chloroplasts and leaves (DCL) proteins [43]. The At telomerase complex to date lacks full characterization, although binding between specific domains of AtTERT and AtTR has been characterized [26], and an interaction between AtTR and AtNAP57 (aka Cbf5 or dyskerin) was identified [44]. Plant and ciliate TR genes share structural and regulatory characteristics that suggest they are transcribed by RNA polymerase III [19]. The recent discovery of plant-type TRs in insects [45] enlarges the number of evolutionarily distant groups sharing the same pathways of TR biogenesis (see [21] and references herein). It is therefore of interest to investigate the specificity of AtLa1 binding to AtTR, including whether such binding is part of telomerase-specific maturation or even if AtLa1 might be a component of the active telomerase complex, given the structural similarity between La and LARP7 protein families. This study determines structural regions of both molecules responsible for AtLa1-TR binding and their affinity. Of secondary interest is the structural basis of AtLa1 binding AtDomino, and if there is an obvious function for the DUF3223 motif, so far found only in plants and ciliates [2, 39–43].

Materials and methods

Preparation of protein and RNA constructs

Preparation of Gateway entry clones and Gateway Y2H destination clones coding for the full-length (FL) AtLa1 (AT4G32720) and DOMINO1 (AT5G62440) was described previously [17]. Constructs for the AtTERT (AT5G16850) TRBD domain for Y3H were prepared previously [26]. Constructs bearing variant AtLa1 and AtDomino fragments were subcloned using specific primers (Supplementary Table S1). Constructs bearing mutated regions of AtLa1 (F331A, D333R, R344A, W387A, SYD124GGG) and AtTR (gg179cc, ggg179cac, gg185cc, gg193cc, gg196cc) were prepared by mutagenesis of AtLa1 plasmids and AtTR plasmids, respectively, using a QuikChange Lightning Site-Directed Mutagenesis Kit (Agilent Technologies, #210519) according to the manufacturer's instructions (all primers are listed in Supplementary Table S1).

Plasmids bearing plant TR constructs of *A. thaliana*, *Scilla peruviana*, *N. sylvestris*, *Allium cepa*, and control construct pCDT1a were prepared previously [19]. RNA constructs coding for snRNA MRP1, U6.26, pre-tRNA-snoR43.1, and the

Figure 1. Specificity and affinity of AtLa1 binding to AtTR. **(A)** Domain organization of La and LARP7 proteins [2, 11, 40]. *Tetrahymena* Mlp1 is based on AlphaFold3 domain predictions and sequence alignments (Supplementary Fig. S3A) and includes an apparent additional xRRM in a region known to bind RNA [40]. Domains are as annotated, '+' or '-' indicates regions of the sequence with correspondingly charged residues at neutral pH. **(B)** AtLa1 EMSA using 1% agarose gel with 80 nM AtTR 1–268 and protein concentrations (nM) as annotated, visualized by fluorescent staining. **(C)** Representative AtLa1 EMSAs with pre-t snoR43.1, pre-t snoR43.1 ΔU, and snoR43.1 substrates [15, 37], as annotated, conditions as (B). White lines have been added to separate panels from the same gel. **(D)** ELISA experiments detecting immunolabelled AtLa1 bound to ≤ 0.5 pmol biotinylated AtTR 1–268 and non-biotinylated competitor RNA as annotated (ytRNA, budding yeast tRNA). Lines show equations fit to data used to calculate KD, average AtTR values are shown in all experiments for comparison, error bars are the standard deviation. **(E)** ELISA experiments as (D) with plant TR competitors (full details in Supplementary Table S2). **(F)** Comparison of AtLa1–AtTR binding assays used in this work. Solid black circles are 1.5 s T-jump data from MST experiments; signal is from 5 nM 3' Cy5-labelled AtTR 1–268. Solid lines show equations fitted to data used to calculate KD (Supplementary Table S3); dotted line is a Hill equation fit with $n = 2$ for comparison, and error bars are standard deviation. Blue closed circles are normalized fractional saturation of 40 nM unlabelled AtTR calculated from band shift distances for EMSAs (Supplementary Fig. S1E), and open blue circles and dotted lines are 1/normalized signal change for ELISA competition experiments [derived from (D) for comparison]. For all experiments other than ELISAs, AtLa1 concentrations are divided by the fold increase in AtTR concentration. **(G)** 1.5 s T-jump from MST experiments with AtLa1 and 5 nM Cy5-labelled pre-tRNA-snoR43.1 constructs as annotated.

5'UTR ATR sequence was amplified from genomic DNA of *A. thaliana* (Col-0) with specific primers (Supplementary Table S1) and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) products were introduced to pCR II TOPO vector (Invitrogen, #K461020). Specific primers for cloning of plant TR constructs were designed using assembled TR subunit sequences of *Pisum sativum*, *Solanum lycopersicum*, *Cestrum elegans*, *Zea mays*, and *Asparagus officinalis* published in [19]. Plant TR se-

quences were amplified using genomic DNA isolated from leaves of *C. elegans* L. [46] or young seedlings of *Z. mays* L., *P. sativum* L., *S. lycopersicum* L., and *A. officinalis* L.; seeds were purchased from local distributors (Nohel Garden, SEMO Smržice). PCR products were introduced to pCRII TOPO vector (Invitrogen, #K461020) and plasmids were sequenced to determine the construct orientation with respect to the universal M13F primer. The AtTR constructs ΔP4

and mP2/3 were prepared previously [26], whereas Δ T/PK (deletion nt 19–171) and P4/5/6 (nt 178–251) constructs were prepared using specific primers listed in [Supplementary Table S1](#). The Δ P6 (deletion nt 201–231) construct was generated using PCR product amplified with specific primers ([Supplementary Table S1](#)), AtTR plasmid as a template, and Phusion® High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #F530L). The Δ P6 plasmid was recovered using PCR product and GeneArt™ Gibson Assembly HiFi Master Mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #A46624) according to the manufacturer's instructions, mutation was verified by plasmid sequencing. AtTR fragments Δ T/PK, Δ P6, and P4/5/6 for Y3H were PCR-amplified (primers specified in [Supplementary Table S1](#)) and ligated into the SmaI site of pIII/MS2-2 vector using NEBuilder® HiFi DNA Assembly Master Mix (New England Biolabs, #E2621S).

Protein expression and purification

The Gateway cloning system (Invitrogen) was used to introduce DNA fragments encoding desired proteins and protein fragments into pDEST15 or pDEST17 Gateway destination vectors according to the manufacturer's instructions. These constructs allow for the expression of proteins with N-terminal glutathione transferase (GST) or poly-histidine (His) tags for affinity purification. Plasmids containing protein constructs were then transformed into Rosetta (DE3) pLysS or BL21-CodonPlus-RIL cells. 0.5–0.6 mM isopropyl-1-thiol- β -D-galactopyranoside was added to the log-phase cell culture to induce protein expression overnight at 20°C–25°C. Cells were harvested at 5000 rpm at 4°C for 15 min and either stored at –80°C for later use or immediately disrupted by sonication in lysis buffer [0.1 M Tris–HCl pH 8.0, 0.5 M NaCl, 0.5% w/v polyethyleneimine (SERVA, #3314103), 1 mM benzamidine-HCl (Carl Roth, #R.CN38.3), 1 mM polymethyl sulfonyl fluoride, with purifications for EMSAs also including 0.5 mM dithiothreitol]. Afterwards, disrupted cells were centrifuged at 20 000 rpm for 10 min at 4°C. The supernatant was applied to SpinTrap GST or Ni Sepharose spin columns (Cytiva, #28-4013-53, #28-9523-59), reused, and periodically refilled with 0.4 ml 50% Glutathione Sepharose® 4 Fast Flow (Cytiva, #17-5132-01) or Ni-NTA agarose Fast Flow resin (Cube Biotech, #31105). Purification proceeded according to the manufacturer's instructions, modified to include three equilibration steps and three washing steps overall. The target protein was then eluted with 0.1 M Tris–HCl pH 8.0, 0.5 M NaCl, with the addition of 40 to 80 mM glutathione or 100 mM imidazole for GST and His purifications, respectively, and 10% glycerol, 1 mM ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), and 0.5 mM dithiothreitol added to this and subsequent buffers for EMSA experiments. Imidazole or glutathione was then reduced to <1 mM concentration by buffer exchange using Amicon® Ultra Centrifugal Filters (Millipore, Merck) and the protein was concentrated as appropriate. La1 and TRBD rapidly lose binding ability over time or with freeze-thaw cycles, so all experiments were performed using proteins purified earlier the same day. Domino stocks were stored at –80°C between experiments. Protein concentrations are estimated values based on 280 nm absorbance measured using a NanoDrop ND-1000 spectrophotometer and extinction coefficient values from *in silico* prediction (ExPaSy ProtParam tool).

RNA synthesis and labelling

RNA was synthesized using HiScribe™ T7 Quick High Yield RNA Synthesis Kit (New England Biolabs, #E2050S) to transcribe a PCR product amplified from pCRII TOPO plasmid DNA sequences using primers detailed in [19, 26] and in [Supplementary Table S1](#). AtTR, AtTR fragments, and other RNA templates (MRP1, U6-26, ATR5'UTR, pre-tRNA-snoR43.1, snoR43.1, and pCDT1a) were produced using PCR products prepared using T7-specific forward and specific reverse primers. For competitive ELISAs, plant TRs were transcribed using a PCR product generated from plasmid DNA using universal M13F and sequence-specific reverse primers ([Supplementary Table S1](#)). RNA was then purified using AMPure XP magnetic beads (Beckman Coulter, #A63881) according to the manufacturer's protocol, eluted in water, and stored at –80°C between experiments. For ELISA or MST experiments, synthesized RNA was 3' labelled with biotin- or Cy5-labelled cytosine bisphosphate, respectively (Thermo Scientific #20160, Jena Biosciences #NU-1706-CY5), using Pierce™ RNA 3' End Biotinylation Kit (Thermo Scientific, #20160) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Labelled RNA was stored away from light at –80°C. Alternatively, 5' Cy5-labelled RNA was instead prepared using a 5' End Tag™ kit (Vector Laboratories, #MB-9001) to dephosphorylate RNA and rephosphorylate with a γ -[S] phosphate group, followed by covalent linkage of S to Cy5-maleimide (Vector Laboratories, #FP-1322–1). The manufacturer's instructions were followed with the exception that the sulphur-maleimide reaction was performed overnight. Efficiency of labelling by this method was generally poor (ca. 10%) following the instructions directly, this was optimized to 60% following overnight maleimide linking, but remained consistently lower efficiency than 3' labelling ($\geq 80\%$ efficiency consistently) in our hands (details in Supplementary information). For north-western blotting ([Supplementary Fig. S1](#)), synthesized RNA was dephosphorylated using incubation with Quick Calf Intestinal Phosphatase (Quick CIP #M0525, New England Biolabs) for 1 h at 37°C, before purification using AMPure XP magnetic beads (Beckman Coulter, #A63881) or High Pure RNA Isolation Kit (Roche, #11828665001) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Dephosphorylated RNA was then rephosphorylated with radioactive 32 P using incubation with γ -[32 P] ATP and T4 polynucleotide kinase (Thermo Scientific, #EK0032) for 1 h at 37°C, followed by purification using MoBiSpin G-50 gel columns (MoBiTech GmbH, #SCO510). Radiolabelled RNA was then stored at –20°C until use. Prior to all experiments, RNA stocks were heated at 95°C for 5 min before immediately being placed on ice to refold.

Electrophoretic mobility shift assays

In vitro synthesized RNA was mixed with protein fragments and variants of specified concentrations in 20 μ l of reaction buffer per sample, with final concentrations of 0.1 M Tris–HCl pH 8.0, 0.5 M NaCl, 10% glycerol, 1 mM benzamidine-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1 mM PMSF, 0.5 mM DTT and typically 80 nM RNA concentration. The mixtures were then incubated on ice for 20 min before the protein–RNA complex was resolved by 1% non-denaturing agarose gel in 1 \times TAE buffer at 4°C for 50 min at 90 V. Gels were stained with 5000 \times diluted EliDNA PS Green (Elisabeth Pharmakon, Czech Republic) in 1 \times standard TAE buffer at room

temperature for 30 min and then imaged using an Amersham™ Imager 680 (GE Healthcare). Gel images are representative examples of experiments repeated at least three times. For La1 WT, the mean displacement of bands from two EMSA repeats using a larger concentration range was measured from the relative position of overlaid lines in Microsoft PowerPoint and further analysed in Microsoft Excel and QTI plot (see below for K_D determination).

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays

Ninety-six-well immuno plates (SPL Life Sciences) were incubated overnight with either 5 µg/ml streptavidin (Sigma–Aldrich, #S4762) at room temperature or 5 µM purified AtLa1 His at 4°C, 50 µl per well in 1× PBS. Plates were washed with 1× phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and then blocked with 3% bovine serum albumin (Sigma–Aldrich, #A3294) for 2–3 h at room temperature. For experiments with RNA, plates were then washed with 1× PBS and then incubated for 1–2 h with 4 nM 3' biotinylated AtTR 1–268 in 5 mM Tris–HCl, 50 mM KCl, 0.01% Triton X-100, pH 7.6. Plates were washed with 1× PBS with 0.05% Tween (PBST) and then incubated with purified GST fusion proteins, pre-incubated with 1:2 anti-GST antibodies (G1160, Sigma–Aldrich), in a range of concentrations as appropriate in 100 mM Tris–HCl, 500 mM NaCl, pH 8.0 for 20 min. Plates were then washed with 1× PBST and then incubated with 0.5% BSA in 1× PBS for 5 min three times before being incubated with 1:1000 secondary anti-mouse antibodies (A0168, Sigma–Aldrich), washed and blocked a further three times in the same way, and then developed using 0.1 mg/ml tetramethylbenzidine (Sigma–Aldrich, #860336) and 0.04% H₂O₂ in 50 mM phospho-citrate buffer pH 5.0 for 5 min. Absorbance at 600 nm was then recorded for each well twice using a Synergy H1 plate reader (Agilent BioTEK). At least two independent repeats of each experiment were performed, with absorbance values normalized, curated, and averaged using Microsoft Excel and QTIplot (IonDev Software, see below for K_D determination).

Microscale thermophoresis

Two-fold serial dilutions of GST fusion proteins were mixed in a 1:1 ratio with Cy5-labelled RNA to give final concentrations of typically 0.2–10 000 nM protein and 5 nM RNA in 50 mM Tris–HCl, 250 mM NaCl, 250 mM potassium acetate, pH 7.0 with 0.05% Tween. Sample preparation took ~5 min before samples were loaded into normal or premium capillaries (NanoTemper), and both initial fluorescence and microscale thermophoresis (MST) measurements for up to 20 s were recorded using 1%–8% power laser excitation and a Monolith NT.115 pico instrument (NanoTemper). Raw data were exported and analysed using Microsoft Excel and QTIplot (IonDev Software, see below for K_D determination). All MST values presented are those recorded at 25°C from the 1.5 s T-jump as in many cases aggregation caused high levels of noise in longer MST traces.

K_D determination

Changes in absorbance (ELISA), band displacement (EMSA), circular dichroism (CD), or fluorescence (MST) data were normalized and then fit to the rearrangement of the standard equation for dissociation constant (K_D) determination:

$$\theta = ([P_0][P]) / (K_D + [P])$$

Where θ is fractional saturation (i.e. the normalized absorbance or fluorescence signal), $[P]$ is protein concentration, and $[P_0]$ is protein concentration in the absence of RNA (defined as 1 or –1 after normalization, depending on the direction of the process). Fittings were performed using QTIplot (IonDev Software) and a scaled Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm for non-linear least-squares fitting. Numbers of replicas for ELISA and MST experiments are given in [Supplementary Tables S2–S4](#).

Yeast two-hybrid assay

The classical Gal4-based Y2H system was used to analyse protein–protein interactions as described previously [47]. Briefly, pGBKT7 and pGADT7 constructs were co-transformed into the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* PJ69–4a strain and selected on SD–Leu, –Trp plates. Drop tests were carried out on SD–Leu, –Trp, and –His (with 0.1; 0.5; 1; 5; 10; 15; and 30 mM 3-aminotriazole) plates at 28°C. Each combination was co-transformed at least three times, and three independent drop tests were carried out.

β -galactosidase assay

Assay was performed as described in [26]. After the transformation of the ~500 ng of each plasmid DNA, single colonies were inoculated into 100 µl of YPD medium (in triplicate) in a 96-well plate and grown overnight at 28°C. The next day, OD₆₀₀ was measured using a BioTEK Powerwave 340 microplate reader (Agilent BioTEK) by diluting 10 µl culture in 90 µl water. The remaining 90 µl of the cultures were washed in 50 µl of Z-buffer (60 mM Na₂HPO₄, 60 mM NaH₂PO₄, 10 mM KCl, 1 mM MgSO₄, pH 7.0), 25 µl of 0.1% SDS was added, followed by addition of 6 µl of chloroform. Reactions were mixed several times by pipetting and incubated for 15 min at 30°C. Next, 60 µl of 4 mg/ml ortho-nitrophenyl- β -galactoside (Sigma–Aldrich, #N1127) was added to each reaction and mixed well. The time of the reaction was recorded. Once the yellow colour appeared, the reactions were stopped by adding 120 µl of 1 M Na₂CO₃ and mixed well. The plate was spun at 2500 rpm for 2 min to remove cell debris. One hundred microlitres of the supernatants were transferred to a new plate, and OD₄₂₀ and OD₅₅₀ were measured using a microplate reader. Miller units were calculated according to the formula:

$$\text{Miller Units} = 1000 \times (\text{OD}_{420} - 1.75 \times \text{OD}_{550}) / (T \times V \times \text{OD}_{600})$$

OD₄₂₀ and OD₅₅₀ are read from the reaction mixture, OD₆₀₀ reflects cell density in the cell suspension, T = time of the reaction in minutes, and V = volume of culture used in the assay in ml. Relative growth in Miller units was then normalized to the highest value (AtLa1 WT), analysed, and presented using Microsoft Excel and QTIplot (IonDev Software).

Yeast three-hybrid assay (Y3H)

The Y3H system [48] was used to map protein–TR interactions as described previously [26]. Briefly, variant AtTR–MS2 (pIII/MS2-2 derived) plasmids and Gal4AD–AtTERT fragments (in pGADT7 derived plasmids) were transformed into *S. cerevisiae* strain YBZ-1 and selected on plates missing leucine and adenine (–LA). RNA–protein interaction was monitored by YBZ-1 cell growth on selection plates missing leucine, adenine, and histidine (–LAH). In addition, increasing concentrations of 3-aminotriazole (3-AT), which competi-

tively inhibits the imidazole glycerol-phosphate dehydratase (product of *HIS3* gene), were used to measure the relative strength of the interaction. Each combination was co-transformed two times, and two independent drop tests were carried out.

A multicomponent variant of the Y3H assay (derived from the multi-component Y2H system [49]) was used to test the effect of La1 on the AtTERT–AtTR interaction. AtTR-MS2, Gal4AD-AtTERT, and Gal4BD-La1 (pGBKT7-derived) plasmids were co-transformed into the YBZ-1 strain and selected on –LWA plates. Empty Gal4AD and Gal4BD plasmids were used as a control. RNA–protein complex stability was monitored on –LWAH plates with or without an increasing concentration of 3-AT. Each combination was co-transformed two times, and two independent drop tests were carried out.

Mass photometry

Samples for mass photometry using a TwoMP instrument (Refeyn, Oxford, UK) were prepared in higher concentrations (AtLa1 100 nM, 1000 nM Domino) in commercial culture-grade Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (Gibco). Samples and buffers were equilibrated to room temperature before measurement, then diluted 20× typically in the final drop. Drops were cast on MassGlass UC (Refeyn) precast microscope slides after sonication in 50% isopropanol followed by washing with milli-Q water to maximize glass cleanliness. Mass values were calibrated against MassFference P1 (Refeyn) and an in-house 40 kDa protein standard, with mass peaks typically giving a linear fit with $R^2 = 1.000$, gradient of –36.62 mDa, maximum mass error of 2.1%, and intercept (contrast) of –0.00007. Sixty-second videos were recorded using AquireMP 2024 R2 software (Refeyn). Events recorded during this time were deconvoluted into mass histograms with 5 kDa-width bars and manually fit to Gaussian profiles using DiscoverMP v2024 R2 software (Refeyn). Following optimization, all measurements were performed at least in triplicate.

Results

La1 binds to snRNA *in vitro*, with a preference for telomerase RNA

In vitro RNA binding experiments were performed with several small nuclear RNAs (snRNA) and other RNA constructs with structural characteristics that could be relevant to protein–RNA interactions. Work started with AtTR, given that AtLa1 copurifies with telomerase [16] but does not bind AtTERT directly [17], which would be rationalized if AtTR binds to AtLa1 as well as AtTERT. Incubating purified FL AtLa1 protein with *in vitro* synthesized AtTR causes a shift in RNA mobility detectable by EMSA (Fig. 1B) consistent with complex formation. Comparable shifts in EMSAs are also observed when AtLa1 is incubated with *in vitro* synthesized variants of the dicistronic pre-t snoR43.1 and snoR43.1 transcripts (Fig. 1C), which are known AtLa1 substrates *in vivo* [15]. AtLa1 also binds a pre-t snoR43.1 construct missing its 3' poly-U trailer (pre-t snoR43.1 Δ U, Fig. 1C) with similar affinity, suggesting at least one other site of RNA substrate recognition is present beyond polyU, similar to human genuine La recognition of (pre-)tRNA (LARP3, [9]).

AtLa1 has high purity when expressed as a fusion with glutathione transferase (GST, Supplementary Fig. S1A and

B). Northwestern hybridization of immobilized proteins with AtTR confirms that the species responsible for RNA binding has the predicted mass of AtLa1, including an excess of unlabelled competitor RNA (Supplementary Fig. S1C). Binding of AtTR to AtLa1 also occurs when GST is replaced with an N-terminal 6×His sequence (Supplementary Fig. S1C). Consistent with this, GST alone does not cause any observable shift in EMSA experiments (Supplementary Fig. S1D).

Flexible roles in RNA binding and chaperone activity are well known in La proteins [2]. Therefore, to investigate the preferences and specificity of AtLa1–RNA binding, competitive ELISA experiments were performed using immobilized 3'-biotinylated AtTR, incubated with immunolabelled La1–GST and various mobile competitor RNAs, including those tested in previous EMSA experiments (Fig. 1D and Supplementary Table S2). Of these, unlabelled AtTR competes with AtLa1–AtTR binding with a higher affinity ($K_D = 41$ nM) than all but snoR43.1 ($K_D = 14$ nM). Guanine quadruplex-forming RNA derived from the 5'-UTR of the ATAXIA TELANGIECTASIA-MUTATED AND RAD3-RELATED (ATR) mRNA [50] competed with the lowest affinity (Fig. 1C, $K_D = 600$ nM). This is followed by polymerase III transcripts U6-26 ($K_D = 260$ nM), mature budding yeast tRNA ($K_D = 220$ nM), and RNase MRP subunit MRP1 ($K_D = 160$ nM). MRP1 binds with essentially identical affinity when the polyU tail is not present (MRP1 Δ U, $K_D = 130$ nM), and the same is true for pre-t snoR43.1 and pre-t snoR43.1 Δ U ($K_D = 150$ nM and $K_D = 100$ nM, respectively). This is in contrast to snoR43.1 and snoR43.1 Δ U, where the latter loses nearly five-fold affinity for AtLa1 ($K_D = 70$ nM) in competitive ELISAs. This difference in affinity might be the molecular basis of the two pathways, where AtLa is proposed to be part of processing the dicistronic pre-t snoR43.1 transcript to mature snoR43.1 [37], and is consistent with a two-site binding model, similar to that proposed for LARP3 (pre-)tRNA recognition [9].

AtLa1 clearly has affinity for multiple pol-III transcripts *in vitro*, consistent with a flexible biological role in pol-III transcript biogenesis. However, its high affinity for TR raises the question of whether it has an additional role in the maturation of telomerase in *A. thaliana* or indeed for plants in general. Plant TRs share similar structural characteristics; therefore, to examine the possibility of a more general mode of AtLa–TR interaction, competitive ELISA RNA–protein binding experiments were performed with AtTR and nine plant TR constructs (Fig. 1E). These constructs included representatives of species with variant telomeric repeats [22]. AtLa1 binds all plant TRs tested with similar affinities regardless of telomere type and evolutionary relationship (Supplementary Table S2). Binding at most has a 2- to 3-fold variability for TRs of *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Brassicales, $K_D = 41$ nM), garden pea (*Pisum sativum*, Fabales, $K_D = 80$ nM), and *Cestrum elegans* (Solanales, $K_D = 90$ nM), the latter which synthesizes variant telomeric repeats. The same is true for other representatives of species with telomere variants, such as monocots maize (*Zea mays*, Poales, $K_D = 60$ nM), *Scilla peruviana* (Asparagales, $K_D = 80$ nM), asparagus (*Asparagus officinalis*, Asparagales, $K_D = 50$ nM), and onion (*Allium cepa*, Asparagales, $K_D = 50$ nM). *Nicotiana sylvestris* (Solanales, $K_D = 42$ nM) also has a comparable affinity, and the same is true for tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*, $K_D = 30$ nM). This is therefore consistent with a hypothesis that there is a general conserved role of La proteins in plant telomerases. This interaction might be simply

explained if there is a sequence or structure in TRs that forms a conserved interface with one or more RNA-binding domains of plant La proteins. Conserved or covariant regions in angiosperm TRs include the pseudoknot-forming P2 and P3 regions, closing P1a stem, and parts of the P4/5/6 stem [20].

AtLa1 binding to AtTR *in vitro* is a dynamic biphasic process

To investigate the molecular basis of this La-TR interaction, which presumably might be generally applicable to land plants, *in vitro* thermodynamic protein–RNA binding experiments were performed. AtTR binding to AtLa1 was investigated in greater detail using microscale thermophoresis (MST, Fig. 1F, Table 1, Supplementary Table S3) using AtLa1 and 3′Cy5-labelled RNA substrates. Data are reported from the first 1.5 s of the experiment, known as the temperature jump (T-jump). This process typically reports on apparent mass changes resulting from *bona fide* protein–RNA complex formation, which for AtLa1–AtTR is biphasic. The fast T-jump process ($K_D = 20 \pm 10$ nM) is consistent with apparent mass changes in EMSAs (blue circles, Fig. 1F) and displacement of the complex with competitor RNA in ELISAs (open blue circles, Fig. 1F). The slow process is often incomplete or unresolved over the concentration ranges used for binding experiments, and so is analysed for completeness where detected, but will not be considered further (Supplementary Table S3). Given that MST has only been widely available for a decade or so (reviewed in [51]) and our novel use of this technique for the detection of specific protein binding to structured RNA, we cross-validated its performance using AtLa1 and its known pre-tRNA substrates [15] (Fig. 1G). The pattern of binding in MST experiments was consistent with ELISA competition data, in that AtLa1 had ~10-fold lower affinity for pre-tsnor43.1, regardless of polyU. In contrast, AtLa1 had high affinity for snoR43.1 ($K_D = 50 \pm 5$ nM), which was reduced 200-fold in the corresponding ΔU construct (Supplementary Table S3). Regardless of the technique employed, AtLa1 therefore exhibits typical genuine La polyU sensitivity, which is presumably coupled with the recognition of other structural factors [9]. To investigate this molecular interface, experiments were performed to determine the binding properties of individual La domains (Fig. 2) and the structural features of AtTR that they recognize in combination with polyU (Fig. 3).

The MST experiments reported here also reveal protein–RNA interactions through changes in the initial capillary fluorescence of Cy5-labelled RNA, in addition to changes in relative fluorescence from the T-jump (Supplementary Fig. S2A). Control experiments with serially diluted Cy5-labelled AtTR confirmed that initial fluorescence values do not affect thermophoresis if absolute fluorescence values fall within manufacturer-recommended limits (Supplementary Fig. S2B). Initial fluorescence changes for AtLa1–AtTR binding are also a biphasic process comparable to classical fluorescence titrations (open circles, Supplementary Fig. S2C and D). The fast process ($K_D = 5 \pm 1$ nM) is one of protein-induced fluorescence quenching (PIFQ, [52]) likely to report on smaller-scale structural changes within the region of the Cy5 label, perhaps preceding *bona fide* binding. The slow process ($K_D = 1.9 \pm 0.2$ μ M) is a protein-induced fluorescence enhancement (PIFE, [53]) that occurs concomitantly with perturbation of the RNA A-type

helical structure monitored by circular dichroism (red circles, Supplementary Fig. S2C, details in Supplementary Fig. S2E). MST experiments using 3′ Cy5-labelled AtTR and its natural binding partner, the TERT telomerase RNA binding domain (TRBD, [26]), have comparable initial fluorescence changes to AtLa1 experiments, which are eliminated when Cy5 is attached to the 5′ end of AtTR, without affecting T-jump affinity (Supplementary Fig. S2F). The same is true for initial fluorescence changes when using AtLa1 (Supplementary Fig. S2F); however, T-jump affinity is also impeded. This suggests that the position of the 5′ Cy5 label may sterically hinder AtLa1 binding to AtTR, but not TRBD binding (Supplementary Fig. S2G). As such, we have used 3′ labelling for all other experiments unless noted, recording K_D values derived from the initial fluorescence processes (Supplementary Table S3), but only considering easily rationalized T-jump information for our description of protein–RNA binding.

According to MST experiments, AtLa1 binding to AtTR is therefore comparable in affinity to the minimal AtTERT RNA-binding domain TRBD (Supplementary Fig. S2F) and to other pol-III transcripts, with these and other affinities summarized in Supplementary Table S3. To explore this further, *in vitro* experiments were performed to attempt to map the location of AtLa1–AtTR interaction at a molecular level, with MST-derived K_D values summarized in Table 1.

La1 binds to telomerase RNA *in vitro* via its C-terminal xRRM domain, stabilized by LaM

Like many genuine La proteins and most LARP7 proteins, AtLa1 has a nonstandard RRM near its C-terminus, in addition to the La motif and adjacent RRM, which together form a La module (LaM) found in the majority of La and LARP proteins (Fig. 1A). Sequence alignments with representative La and LARP7 proteins and AlphaFold3 structural predictions indicate that this domain shares characteristic features of the extended helical RRM (xRRM) of *Tetrahymena* p65, including an RNP3-like RNA recognition sequence, a lack of single-stranded RNA binding sequences RNP1 and RNP2 found in canonical RRM (Supplementary Fig. S3A, [35]) and a third predicted alpha helix in addition to the two found in canonical RRM (Supplementary Fig. S3A). Genuine La proteins, except for recently reported *in vitro* experiments for human LARP3 [14], have not been implicated as having a specific role in binding TR; however, the LARP7 family, absent in plants, has evolutionarily diverse members with well-characterized TR-binding properties [2]. AtLa1 has a similar predicted domain structure (Fig. 1A) to TR-binding *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* Pof8 [34, 35] and *Tetrahymena thermophila* p65 [10]. Small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) data are consistent with these predictions and correlate to an ensemble of models where structured LaM and xRRM domains are freely mobile in solution, joined with a flexible linker (Supplementary Fig. S3B–D and Supplementary Table S6). To determine which domain(s) in AtLa1 are responsible for AtTR binding, the protein was expressed as a selection of fragments containing one or more of these domains (Fig. 2A).

EMSAs detect a change in apparent AtTR mass is consistent with complex formation in fragments containing the C-terminal amino acids 236–433, including the minimal fragment xRRM itself, which exhibits a modest, but distinct shift consistent with its lower mass compared to FL or 106–433

Table 1. K_D values calculated from MST experiments at 25°C

La1	AtTR	MST [nM]	La1	AtTR	MST [nM]
FL	1–268	20 ± 10	xRRM	1–268	220 ± 30
	mP2/3	5 ± 2		mP2/3	19 ± 8
	T/PK	1000 ± 200		T/PK	590 ± 90
	ΔT/PK	16 ± 7		ΔT/PK	28 ± 5
	ΔP4	560 ± 70		ΔP4	40 ± 10
	ΔP6	130 ± 30		ΔP6	14 ± 7
	P4/5/6	34 ± 9		P4/5/6	90 ± 30
	ΔU	70 ± 10		ΔU	20 ± 10
	uuu	2100 ± 300		uuu	n.d.
	ccc	n.d.			
	LaM	1–268		1200 ± 300	F331A
mP2/3		70 ± 40	D333R	1–268	29 ± 4
T/PK		170 ± 20	R344A	1–268	550 ± 60
ΔT/PK		2000 ± 500	W387A	1–268	230 ± 50
ΔP4		2100 ± 300			
ΔP6		30 ± 20			
P4/5/6		600 ± 100			
ΔU		20 ± 10			
uuu		2700 ± 300			

MST values are calculated from the first 1.5 s of thermophoresis (T-jump) fast process; n.d., not detectable. Error values are from K_D fittings; further data are presented in [Supplementary Table S3](#).

fragments (Fig. 2B). In contrast, fragments lacking these residues show no change in apparent AtTR mass over the concentration range explored. For a quantitative measurement of AtTR binding, MST was employed (K_D values are summarized in Table 1 and [Supplementary Fig. S3](#)), focusing on amino acids 1–206, which encompass the LaM, and amino acids 236–433, which contain the xRRM (Fig. 2C). LaM has 60× less affinity for AtTR than the FL protein, whereas xRRM has an 11× lower affinity. This suggests that the xRRM has the bigger impact on AtTR affinity of the two domains, consistent with observations from EMSAs. For both fragments, the addition of 100× excess unlabelled budding yeast tRNA competitor has no effect on AtTR affinity (Fig. 2C, lower panel, dotted lines), suggesting that these isolated RNA-binding domains have greater specificity than the FL protein. It is perhaps also noteworthy that the AtTR affinity of AtLa1 FL and xRRM in the presence of competitor RNA are approximately the same, suggesting that the xRRM is at least responsible for the majority of specific AtTR affinity.

The xRRM RNA-binding motif termed RNP3 found in human, alveolate, and yeast xRRM domains has the sequence Y/W-X-D/Q ([Supplementary Fig. S3A](#)). The sequence in AtLa1 differs only in that the first amino acid is F, rather than Y or W. Given that both Pof8 and p65 also bind to their respective TR *via* their C-terminal xRRM domain [10, 34], this suggests a conserved RNA binding mode shared by AtLa1 and LARP7 proteins. As such, we propose that the RNP3 motif [35] can include any aromatic residue, pending full structural characterization. The xRRM fragment used here is partially disordered, but maintains a structured core with typical conserved features ([Supplementary Fig. S3E](#) and [Supplementary Table S6](#)). Conserved AtLa1 xRRM residues F³³¹, D³³³, and R³⁴⁴ are predicted to form part of β-sheet 2 and 3 (β2, β3), and conserved α-helix 3 (α3) residues Y³⁸⁶ and W³⁸⁷ are key parts of the p65 TR binding interface in *Tetrahymena* [11, 31]. Pof8 and p65 variants with RNP3 residues replaced had reduced binding affinity for TR [10, 34]. Structural models of these proteins also identify all these conserved residues present as part of the TR-binding side face of the xRRM [11, 35], which is also present in models of AtLa1 pre-

dicted by AlphaFold [54, 55] ([Supplementary Fig. S3F](#)). Point mutant variants of the FL protein were prepared for F³³¹, R³⁴⁴, and W³⁸⁷, where aromatic residues capable of pi-stacking interactions with nucleotides or phosphate backbone-attractive positively charged residues were replaced with non-binding A. Following the example of Hu *et al.* [34], D³³³ was instead replaced with R to create a D333R variant where this charge was reversed and not just annulled.

EMSA of AtLa1 point variants identified that R344A or W387A clearly lower binding affinity, whereas there is minimal change for RNP3 variants F331A or D333R (Fig. 2D). MST experiments are consistent with this, in that F331A and D333R variants have T-jump data within error of wild-type (WT) AtLa1 (Table 1), whereas R344A and W387A show reduced binding (Fig. 2E). For R344A, affinity is 27× lower, compared with W387A, where it is only 11× lower. This confirms that conserved xRRM residues R³⁴⁴ and W³⁸⁷ likely retain a structural role in TR binding in AtLa1, whereas F³³¹ and D³³³ do not.

La1 binds to the stem-loop region between P5 and P6, and the three-way junction region of TR *in vitro*

Having determined the AtLa1 features responsible for AtTR binding, the next obvious question is which structural features of AtTR these RNA binding domains interact with. Of consideration were features typical for all TRs, such as the pseudoknot and template region (T/PK); specific AtTR features, such as the P4/5/6 stem-loop and the three-way junction (TWJ); and regions typical for RNA Pol-III transcripts, such as 3′ poly-U tails (Fig. 3A). Fragments and truncations of AtTR were synthesized *in vitro* and used for binding assays (Fig. 3, K_D values are summarized in Table 1 and [Supplementary Figs S2](#) and [S3](#)). Many of the AtTR constructs used here were previously used to demonstrate *in vivo* binding to AtTERT [26], giving confidence that they fold into biologically relevant structures. For several additional constructs, yeast-3-hybrid (Y3H) experiments under identical conditions as in [26] were performed with the TRBD (telomerase-RNA binding domain) constructs of AtTERT ([Supplementary Fig. S4A](#)), showing

Figure 2. AtLa1 xRRM domain is predominantly responsible for AtTR binding. **(A)** Domain structure of AtLa1, including LaM (grey) and xRRM (red), as predicted by AlphaFold2 [55] and visualized using ChimeraX [56]. xRRM residues chosen for mutagenesis studies are shown in a magnified panel [the same colour scheme is used in panels (B–E)]. Binding of AtLa1 fragments **(B, C)** and AtLa1 FL with point variants of xRRM residues **(D, E)** to AtTR investigated by EMSA (B, D) and MST (C, E). **(B, D)** Representative band shift of 80 nM AtTR 1–268 caused by binding of AtLa1 protein constructs (concentrations in nM) is visualized in agarose gel by fluorescent staining. White lines have been added to separate panels in the same gel (full image in [Supplementary Fig. S1D](#)). **(C, E)** MST 1.5 s T-jump data (lower panels) for 3′ Cy5-labelled AtTR 1–268 and La1 fragments as indicated, with average AtLa1 FL data from Fig. 1F reproduced for comparison. Open symbols and dashed lines in panel (C) show data in the presence of 100× excess unlabelled tRNA competitor. Lines show equations fit to data used to calculate K_D ; error bars are the standard deviation.

results consistent with the known model of AtTR–AtTERT binding.

As a first step in mapping the AtTR–AtLa1 interaction, competition ELISAs were performed with AtLa1 FL (Fig. 3B and [Supplementary Table S2](#)). These show most RNA constructs binding with similar preference as AtTR 1–268 ($K_D = 41$ nM), except for constructs with just the T/PK region ($K_D = 190$ nM) and just the P4/5/6 stem loop ($K_D = 500$ nM). This suggests that preferential AtTR binding may require the presence of the TWJ and/or 3′ and 5′-formed P1a stem that is absent in both constructs.

ELISA competition experiments were also performed using AtLa1 FL and AtTR constructs synthesized with many variant ends (Figs. 3C and D and [Supplementary Fig. S4B](#)), including that first reported for ‘ATR8,’ 1–259 [25] and those with or without poly-U motifs. Affinities only vary by a factor of 10 ($K_D = 9$ nM to 90 nM) but seem to follow a pattern that relates to the length of the 3′ end or, conversely, the amount of the 5′ end that is exposed (Fig. 3C), consid-

ering that both termini form the closing P1a stem together, assuming published models of TR [20] are accurate. The model for AtLa1 binding is therefore justified in including this P1a stem, with an ssRNA overhang presumably affecting recognition or stability of interaction in this experiment. EMSAs were also performed for all AtLa1 domain fragments and mutants ([Supplementary Fig. S1D](#)) to compare AtLa1 1–268 and 1–262 missing the 3′ poly-U trailer (ΔU). Consistent with observations for pre-tsnRNA, EMSAs with ΔU appear unchanged. These observations therefore suggest that high-affinity AtLa1–AtTR binding, unlike snoR43.1 binding, relies on RRM sensitivity to ssRNA content and structure more than La motif recognition of 3′ sequence. To examine 3′ sequence sensitivity further, MST experiments were performed with 5′ Cy5-labelled 10 nt oligonucleotides replicating the predicted 3′ AtTR terminus ending in 3′ UUU-OH (uuu, [20], Fig. 3C black frame), which lack any predicted structured regions (Fig. 3E). AtLa1 FL has low, but detectable affinity ($K_D = 2.1$ μ M) for this sequence, which is abolished when the last three

Figure 3. Mapping La1 domain binding to AtTR. **(A)** Overview and legend of representative AtTR constructs used in La1 binding experiments (**B–H**), template (cyan), and deleted P4 (red) region are highlighted. **(B)** ELISA competition experiments detecting immunolabelled AtLa1 bound to ≤ 0.5 pmol biotinylated AtTR 1–268 and non-biotinylated competitor AtTR fragments. **(C)** Sequence of AtTR with colour-coded endings as in [Supplementary Fig. S4B](#). Purple highlight shows cytosine 259, which is assumed to be the last duplex-binding base of the 3' terminus; black frame denotes the oligonucleotide sequence used in panel (E). **(D)** K_D values from AtLa1 ELISA competition experiments, as in (B), but with varying AtTR 3' termini. The line shows fitting to a Gaussian distribution centred on 275 nt. **(E, F, G, H)** MST 1.5 s T-jump data for (E) 5' Cy5-labelled 10 nt RNA oligonucleotides (uuu, CCAAUUAUUU; ccc, CCAAUACC) and AtLa1 constructs as annotated, or 5 nM 3' Cy5-labelled AtTR fragments and La1 FL (C), LaM (D), or xRRM (E). Lines show equations fit to data used to calculate K_D . **(I)** Schema of AtTR regions which bind AtLa1 (LaM (grey) or xRRM (red) domains). Possible binding sites are shown in black and unlikely/nonspecific binding sites in light grey.

nucleotides are replaced with C (ccc, Fig. 3E). For these experiments, the T-jump results in a protein-dependent increase in RNA mobility, suggesting that the AtLa1-oligonucleotide complex is more compact than unbound ssRNA. These MST experiments were then repeated with AtLa1 domains; LaM alone has similar affinity for uuu, although xRRM has no affinity for this sequence (Table 1). Together, these observations confirm that the LaM (likely *via* the La motif) has a typical genuine La-like affinity for 3' trailers, which is outcompeted by (x)RRM affinity for other AtTR features.

Therefore, to map these AtTR binding features in detail, AtTR fragment-binding MST experiments were performed with AtLa1 FL, followed by the LaM and xRRM fragments to examine the role of the individual domains.

For AtLa1 FL, there is reduced affinity for the T/PK construct compared to 1–268 (Fig. 3F upper panel, Table 1). This suggests that the T/PK is dispensable for FL binding, consistent with ELISA data, and with an observation that the construct Δ T/PK and the P4/5/6 stem have T-jump data comparable with AtTR 1–268. Similar reduced affinity is observed for a construct missing the P4 region and the poly-U tail (Δ P4, [26]), suggesting that P4 is part of or close to a binding site. A construct shortened by the distal part of the P6 region (Δ P6, Fig. 3D lower panel) also has lowered T-jump affinity, consistent with the idea that there is a binding site on the P4/5/6. Paired regions of P4/5/6 are formed by guanine doublet/triplets (Supplementary Fig. S4C). Thus, we investigated AtLa1 binding to several AtTR variants mutated within these regions. Modification of AtTR guanines 185–186 to cytosine reduces the affinity of the T-jump affinity 7 \times compared to AtTR 1–268 (Supplementary Fig. S4D and Supplementary Table S3). In contrast, there is no change when other guanine stretches along the P4/5/6 stem are modified, consistent with the idea of a binding site between P5 and P6 stems. MST measurements seem to offer greater sensitivity than EMSA data or ELISA competition experiments regarding the AtTR Δ U construct compared to AtTR 1–268, which shows a modest, but clear 3.5 \times loss of affinity for AtLa1 FL (Fig. 3F lower panel, Supplementary Table S3). Finally, a construct modifying the P2 and P3 base pairing regions so that the pseudoknot cannot form (mP2/3, Fig. 3F lower panel) was investigated. The mP2/3 construct is catalytically inactive [20] and unable to bind TRBD [26]; however, it has a slightly higher affinity T-jump process (3 \times) compared to AtTR 1–268. This suggests that disrupting the highly structured pseudoknot region may allow the formation of alternative structures that might be a possible artefactual target for RNA-binding proteins.

The most striking difference between AtLa1 FL binding to various AtTR constructs and binding of LaM is its preference to bind the T/PK construct (Fig. 3G upper panel) as well as Δ P6, Δ U, and mP2/3 (Fig. 3G lower panel) constructs. Removing the possibility of the pseudoknot structure formation in the mP2/3 does not affect LaM binding. This suggests that overlapping parts among these constructs might be involved in specific recognition by this protein domain. Namely, TWJ-adjacent regions of T/PK and possibly the P1a stem. The binding affinities of xRRM to AtTR constructs are similar to AtLa1 FL and quite opposite to LaM. Only T/PK has slightly reduced binding affinity compared to AtTR 1–268, having a 2 \times lower fast T-jump process (Fig. 3H upper panel). All other constructs bind with 1–268-like affinity or greater, suggesting that overall T/PK, P6, 3' polyU, and curiously even the P4

stem are dispensable for xRRM binding (Fig. 3H lower panel, Supplementary Table S3).

Considering these observations together, it is clear, especially from ELISA competition experiments, that AtLa1 FL likely has two binding sites on AtTR, consistent with having two structured RNA-binding domains. The FL protein does not require either the distal P6 end of the P4/5/6 stem or the T/PK for high-affinity binding (Fig. 3F and I). The LaM likely recognizes the adjacent regions of TWJ, perhaps together with the templating region and the connecting stem-loop and P1a stem (Fig. 3G and I). The xRRM binding is sensitive to the central region of the P4/5/6 stem-loop between P5 and P6, although it cannot be ruled out that it has some interaction with the TWJ adjacent regions (Fig. 3H and I). Assuming that the domains both sterically hinder each other from binding to identical or adjacent sites, this therefore suggests a model where one domain binds to the mid-P4/5/6 stem, between P5 and P6 (probably xRRM), and another near to the TWJ (probably LaM), perhaps stabilized by the adjacent stem-loop leading to the T/PK. The observation that the Δ P4 construct of AtTR binds poorly to AtLa1 FL, but is not involved in LaM or xRRM binding is also rationalized if the absence of this stem merely brings the binding regions close enough that there is steric hindrance for both binding events to take place.

Overall, this fragment analysis suggests that AtLa1 binding to AtTR very much resembles the binding of *Tetrahymena* p65 to its equivalent TR [11]. Given the similar affinity for AtLa1 and diverse plant TRs, this model of La binding to TR may also apply to many, if not all, land plants. Another similarity between ciliates and plants is the presence of DUF3223 found in AtDomino, the one known protein interactor of AtLa1 [17].

Domino contains a novel RNA-binding domain and binds to a three-amino-acid motif in the La1 RRM

AtLa1 was previously reported to bind to AtDomino, a plant-specific protein of unknown function, which also binds AtTERT *via* its telomerase-specific N-terminal domain [17]. Given that AtDomino shares an otherwise unique RNA-binding domain with the genuine La proteins of ciliates, and currently it is the best-characterized protein interactor of AtLa1 [17, 38], experiments were performed to further investigate the molecular interface between these proteins.

To initially identify the domain(s) in AtLa1 responsible for AtDomino binding, the yeast 2-hybrid (Y2H) assay was used with the same library of AtLa1 fragments generated to study AtLa1–AtTR binding (Fig. 4A). Consistent with previous reports using this technique [17], AtLa1 FL binds AtDomino strongly, as evidenced by growth in the presence of up to 30 mM aminotriazole, compared to an empty AD vector control (Fig. 4B, Supplementary Fig. S5A). Similar binding was observed for AtLa1 fragments LaM (aa 1–206), Δ xRRM (aa 1–236), and Δ La motif (aa 106–433). In contrast, fragments La motif (aa 1–116) and xRRM (aa 236–433) show much reduced growth, suggesting that residues 116–206 contain the critical region for AtDomino binding. This is also the region of the AtLa1 sequence, which forms the canonical RRM domain, and AlphaFold3 [54] predictions of the AtLa1–AtDomino complex model a loop containing residues S¹²⁴, Y¹²⁵, and D¹²⁶ as the main binding interface (Fig. 4A). These residues were replaced with glycine in the La1 variant SYD124GGG, and the binding of AtDomino was investigated using both *in vivo* Y2H assays and quantitative *in vitro* ELISA.

Figure 4. AtLa1 binds AtDomino via a three-amino acid motif. **(A)** AlphaFold3 prediction [54] of AtLa1–AtDomino complex showing AtLa1 LaM (La motif and RRM, grey) and xRRM (red), and AtDomino DUF3223 (yellow) domains. Highlighted panel shows interacting AtLa1 residues (green) on the RRM-DUF3223 interface. Structural visualizations prepared using ChimeraX [56]. **(B)** Yeast 2-hybrid and **(C)** semi-quantitative β -galactosidase assays pairing Gal4 binding domain (BD) fused AtLa1 fragments and variants with Gal4 activation domain (AD) fused AtDomino. For panel (B), numbers refer to mM concentrations of 3-AT in the growth media; letters refer to amino acids absent for growth. For panel (C), BD-fused AtLa1 (purple bars) are compared to empty BD (grey bars), error bars represent standard deviation. Expression of BD-constructs in yeast cultures is documented in [Supplementary Fig. S5C](#). **(D)** *In vitro* ELISA detecting AtDomino bound to immobilized AtLa1 WT (black circles) and AtLa1 SYD124GGG (dark red stars). Lines show equations fit to data used to calculate K_D . **(E)** Domain structure of AtLa1 and AtDomino, showing protein–protein (black arrows) and protein–RNA interactions (green bars); predicted domains are annotated, and ‘+’ or ‘–’ indicates regions of the sequence with correspondingly charged residues at neutral pH. **(F)** Mass photometry (MP) representative deconvoluted mass spectra of samples with AtLa1 or AtLa1 + AtDomino. Solid lines show Gaussian fittings annotated with average mass values in kDa, numbers in grey are peaks that cannot be unambiguously assigned (more details in [Supplementary Table S5](#)). **(G)** MST 1.5 s T-jump data for AtDomino (black diamonds) and AtDomino delC (green diamonds) with 5 nM 3’ Cy5-labelled AtTR 1–268. For comparison, AtDomino interaction with Cy5-AtTR in the presence of excess unlabelled ytrNA competitor (open black diamonds, dashed lines) is shown. Lines show equations fitted to data used to calculate K_D , error bars represent standard deviation.

The results from Y2H assays show that La1 SYD124GGG is no longer capable of binding AtDomino (Fig. 4B), further confirmed with semi-quantitative Y2H β -galactosidase assays (Fig. 4C). ELISA experiments (Fig. 4D) demonstrated a >10-fold reduced affinity for AtDomino in the SYD124GGG variant, compared to WT AtLa1. It is therefore assumed that the AlphaFold3 prediction of the AtLa1–AtDomino structure is

accurate in this regard. In contrast, AtLa1 xRRM variants with reduced AtTR affinity or specificity (e.g. R344A, Fig. 4B, and others in [Supplementary Fig. S5A](#)), bind AtDomino the same as AtLa1 WT, consistent with the prediction that AtTR binding and AtDomino binding both depend on different (domain) interfaces of AtLa1 (Fig. 4E). To investigate the stoichiometry of AtLa1-Domino binding, *in vitro* mass

photometry experiments were performed. His-tagged proteins were used to avoid the possibility of GST dimerization (Fig. 4F), also taking advantage of the technical point that the AtDomino monomer (23 kDa) is below the limit of detection by this technique ([57], reviewed in [58]). The deconvoluted spectrum of AtLa1 alone has a major peak centred on 55 kDa, consistent with the predicted mass of this protein (48 kDa). When AtDomino is present in a 1:1 ratio, there is a new peak at 76 kDa, consistent with the +23 kDa mass increase of AtLa1 binding a single AtDomino, confirming 1:1 stoichiometry.

AtDomino contains the same domain of unknown function present in the recently identified genuine La proteins of ciliates [2], which is proposed to be a novel RNA-binding domain. MST experiments with AtDomino and fluorescent-labelled AtTR reveal changes of fluorescence and thermophoresis similar to that observed for AtLa1 (Fig. 4G), giving confidence that AtDomino is indeed an RNA-binding protein. AtDomino has 7.5× lower affinity for AtTR 1–268 compared to AtLa1, and this affinity is 4× less in the presence of 1000× excess unlabelled budding yeast tRNA competitor. The AtDomino sequence has a large number of positively charged residues at the C-terminus (Fig. 4E); to eliminate the idea that Domino binding is due to simple electrostatic attraction (e.g. [59]) and not the presence of the domain of unknown function DUF3223, MST experiments were also performed with an AtDomino construct missing the C-terminus (DelC). DelC binds AtTR 1–268 with an affinity within error of AtDomino (Fig. 4G). As the N-terminal sequence of AtDomino is mostly residues expected to have RNA-repulsive negative charge at neutral pH, it is therefore likely that the RNA-binding properties of AtDomino predominantly arise from DUF3223. Repeats of key Y2H experiments confirmed that AtDominoDelC still comparably binds AtLa1 (Supplementary Fig. S5B), suggesting that DUF3223 is also the site responsible for protein–protein interactions with AtLa1 (Fig. 4E), also consistent with structural predictions (Fig. 4A). Initial MST experiments with AtDomino in the presence of AtTR fragments used to map AtLa1 binding do not show the clear-cut differences as observed for AtLa1; however, beyond a modest 3× loss of affinity for ΔT/PK (Supplementary Fig. S5D).

AtDomino therefore has both protein-binding and RNA-binding capabilities, which seemingly result from its single predicted structured domain. Although AtDomino binds to a semi-conserved loop in AtLa1 and has known interactions with AtTERT and other telomerase-related proteins [17], it still remains a question whether these binding activities have relevance to AtTR biogenesis.

La1 enhances TERT binding to TR in yeast three-hybrid experiments

The next point to consider is whether AtLa1 binding to AtTR is compatible with AtTERT binding, which would explain why it is detected in AtTERT pulldowns [16]. This question was addressed *in vivo* using a multi-component yeast 3-hybrid system (Fig. 5A). These experiments are similar to those performed previously to investigate AtTERT–AtTR binding [26], with the addition of constructs encoding for additional proteins (taken from the Y2H system) in the same cell. In this experiment, BD-fused constructs are not used to test the canonical AD–BD interaction as in Y2H, but rather serve as a means of selecting for the presence of the La1 protein in yeast cells (Supplementary Fig. S5E). For these experiments, TRBD was

investigated with or without an unstructured linker that stabilizes TR binding [26]. Yeast with the AtTR-MS2 construct, TRBD AD constructs, and AtLa1 BD can tolerate growth in the presence of higher 3-AT, compared to when an empty BD replaces AtLa1. Curiously, the effect is even more pronounced for yeast with AtLa1 fragment LaM (aa 1–206) and LaΔxRRM (aa 1–236), suggesting that the LaM is the key domain for TRBD binding enhancement. This is consistent with the idea that a complex of AtLa1:TRBD:TR forms at least transiently (Fig. 5B), and that AtLa1 binding to AtTR serves to increase the probability of AtTERT binding telomerase subsequently, reminiscent of the stepwise system in ciliates [60].

Discussion

La1 binds polymerase III transcripts *in vitro* with substrate-specific structural or 3' trailer dependence

Previous studies showed that AtLa1 binds to polymerase III transcripts *in vivo*, specifically precursors for tRNA^{Met} and tRNA-snoR43.1, which both feature a 3' poly-U tail [15]. Data from this study described *in vitro* binding in the 100 nM range for several more polymerase III transcripts, consistent with the typical role of La proteins in binding these transcripts for protective or regulatory reasons [2, 4, 5, 40]. Of the transcripts tested here, AtTR has affinity and specificity comparable to pre-tsnoR43.1. This suggests that AtLa1 has a role in the early steps of plant telomerase biogenesis; however, copurification of AtLa1 with AtTERT [16] raises more possibilities that will be discussed below. Consistent with a proposed sensitivity to 3' tails [15], the AtLa1 protein is somewhat sensitive to this part of AtTR, something that is known as a key marker of polymerase III transcript recognition and maturation in eukaryotes ([5, 6, 40], reviewed in [3]). Similar to observations from genuine human La [9], the *in vitro* experiments in this study show no obvious correlation between binding efficiency of structured RNAs and the uracil content of the 3' terminus of either AtTR, dicistronic pre-tsnoR43.1, or MRP1, although this preference is marked for constructs of snoR43.1 transcript mimicking two processing pathways suggested in [37] and for short oligonucleotides mimicking the AtTR 3' trailer in isolation. This suggests that AtLa1 binding specificity relies on a human-like two-site model, of which 3' trailers are only part [9]. Apparent differences between pull-down experiments [15] and our *in vitro* solution experiments may also relate to the physical stability of La-RNA binding, which is reinforced by poly-U content in human genuine La [7]. Another factor may be the instability of AtLa1, which in our experience loses substantial RNA binding affinity the day after purification, regardless of storage. As with many other La proteins, including *Tetrahymena* p65 [11] and *Trypanosoma brucei* genuine La [5], it is still the classic La module found in most genuine La proteins [2] that is likely to be responsible for interacting with the 3' terminus of RNA. Different 3' ends have been reported for AtTR by [25] and [20], and whilst there is a 10-fold variability in K_D , suggesting a link to 5' or 3' terminus exposure, there is no obvious single preferred form for AtLa1 binding among the constructs tested here. There is the possibility that AtTR exists *in vivo* as variant molecules in different stages of 3' processing or as variant molecules that function in different biological processes, e.g. telomerase [19] or heat-shock responses [25]. It is also known

Figure 5. RNA-binding complexes of AtLa1. **(A)** Multicomponent yeast three-hybrid experiments pairing AtTR 1–268 MS2 or MS2 only with AD constructs of AtTERT TRBD variants in the presence of AtLa1 BD or empty BD constructs, as annotated. Numbers refer to mM concentrations of 3-AT in growth media, letters refer to amino acids absent for growth. **(B)** Schematic of partial AtTERT-TR-La1 complex omitting AtTERT TEN, RT, and CTE domains. LaM in grey, xRRM in red, TRBD in pink, and RNA-binding linker in cyan.

that other plant TRs exist *in vivo* as multiple conformers, only one of which has the templating region exposed [61], a situation also recently reported in humans [62]. In this case, AtLa1 may act as a method of selecting one or more forms of AtTR that are suitable for a role in telomerase. This could be similar to how fission yeast LARP7 protein Pof8 selects correctly folded telomerase RNA with the aid of the LSm2-8 complex [34] or like the proposed human situation where H2A and H2B promote ‘open’ conformers [62]. Moreover, TR exists as gene paralogs in many plant species; if plant La proteins are part of the quality control mechanism of TR, this suggests they may also be one part of what allows for adaptive evolution of these molecules [63], as reviewed in [21].

La1 could fill some roles of the missing LARP7 protein in plant telomerase

Identification of AtLa1 as a major species present in AtTERT pulldown experiments [16] raises the question why this protein is so prevalent and what its telomerase-related role might be. The former is explained by *in vitro* experiments where AtLa1 binds with high affinity ($K_D < 100$ nM) to AtTR and TR from several evolutionarily distant plant species. AtTR would certainly be expected in AtTERT pulldown experiments, so the presence of AtLa1 is explained by binding to this copurified AtTR. The model of AtLa1 binding to AtTR presented here features strong binding *via* the AtLa1 xRRM domain to the stem-loops between P5 and P6. This area has multiple predicted single-stranded loops with a high proportion of conserved nucleotides [20]. Variation of the double-stranded regions changes AtLa1 affinity little, other than the P5 stem, which has a modest effect on binding. As such, the single-stranded sequences are likely the primary site of binding, consistent with what is known about xRRMs [64, 65]. Other plant TRs show conformational variation both *in vivo* and *in vitro* [61], including in these stem-loop regions, so it could be speculated that these loops may provide some sort

of barcode or recognition site for AtLa1 binding, if this protein does have a role in selecting specific TR conformers. Ciliate LARP7 proteins, exemplified by *Tetrahymena* p65, bind to their respective telomerase RNA *via* very similar structural interfaces [11, 32]. This suggests that AtLa1 and perhaps other plant La proteins bind TR for a larger proportion of their lifetime, fulfilling one of the roles attributed to LARP7 proteins, which are absent in plants [2]. AtTERT is known to bind AtTR *via* the PK region and the P4 stem [26], and we observe that AtLa1 increases the affinity of the AtTERT binding domain for AtTR *in vivo*. It might be tempting, therefore, to speculate that AtLa1 could act as a telomerase accessory protein as part of the *in vivo* active telomerase complex, something that is well characterized for yeast and ciliate LARP7 proteins [10, 11, 34]. So far, only AtNAP57 (aka Dyskerin or CBF5) has been proposed as a telomerase accessory protein in plants based on similarity to the human model [44], although its typical H/ACA RNA binding motif is not present in AtTR, and it was not detected in AtTERT pulldown experiments [16]. *In vitro*, AtNAP57 binds to approximately the same part of AtTR as AtLa1 with similar affinity [44]. This is rationalized if these proteins are involved in different steps of AtTR maturation. Indeed, if plant TR is pseudouridinylated by the H/ACA snoRNP complex, of which AtNAP57 is proposed to be the catalytic subunit [66], this could be one explanation for a high-affinity, but low-duration binding interaction as part of AtTR biogenesis. *Arabidopsis thaliana* also has another genuine La protein, AtLa2, although currently all that is known about this is that most likely it cannot complement the RNA maturation functions in yeast and does not bind pre-tRNAs and pre-tsnRNA transcripts *in vivo* [15]. From the perspective of our study, it can be pointed out that the AtLa2 equivalent of the AtLa1 xRRM TR-interacting residue R³⁴⁴ is W, suggesting that this protein would not bind AtTR competently. Moreover, both genes are expressed *in vivo*, but differ in their tissue-specific expression, with AtLa1 mRNA levels highest in tissues composed of actively dividing, i.e. telomerase-active,

cells. This is in contrast to AtLa2, which is more abundant in differentiated cells and senescent organs (see [15] and RNA-seq analysis at TraVA database [67]).

Plant La xRRM binding of TR *in vitro* is more like ciliates than yeast

The main driving force for AtLa1 binding of AtTR is its xRRM domain, distinguished from classic RRM domains by its additional helix and a change in RNP motifs [35]. Typical RRM structure would suggest that aromatic residues are important to form a clamp for pi-stacking interactions, which passes along an RNA chain until a specific sequence binds according to the environment of the pocket [64, 65]. Based on sequence conservation and AtTR binding studies of point variants, we initially assumed that W³⁸⁷ and F³³¹ together form this clamp in AtLa1. Variation of the former decreases the affinity of binding, whereas the latter has no obvious effect on the AtLa1–TR interaction. The role of F³³¹ is therefore one of the differences between the plant system and others, considering the modest change in TR affinity of a minimal p65 xRRM domain, where the corresponding Y⁴⁰⁷ is modified to A [10], and the ~14-fold loss of yeast TR affinity where Y³³⁰ is modified to A in Pof8 [34]. Pof8 binding to fission yeast telomerase RNA is in contrast with the plant/ciliate system, in that both LaM and xRRM have recognition sites on the equivalent of the T/PK loop, and 3' binding is achieved by protein–protein interaction with the LSm2-8 complex that binds at this site [34]. Given that yeast TRs are typically much larger (>1200 nt) than plant or ciliate equivalents (~200–300 nt), it is no surprise that a LARP7 protein of similar size to that in plants/ciliates requires additional help to span and fold this massive molecule.

In addition to RRM clamp residues, adjacent residue R³⁴⁴ appears to have a more essential, conserved role in AtTR binding, presumably using positive charge for electrostatic attraction or steering of the substrate. Modifying the corresponding p65 or Pof8 R to A results in a six-fold or five-fold loss of RNA binding affinity, respectively, comparable to the eight-fold loss of binding for AtLa1. Another nearby residue, D³³³, has no obvious effect on binding affinity if it is switched from negative to positive, unlike the eight-fold loss of TR affinity for the corresponding Pof8 variant. In p65, the equivalent of this residue interacts with the aromatic ring of guanine-121, part of the GU-bulge essential for p65 binding [11] (Fig. 6), suggesting that this residue may be important for sequence/structure recognition in ciliates, but not plants.

Although hardly surprising, AlphaFold3 predictions of the AtLaM, AtxRRM, and AtTERT [54] overlay p65 and TERT well in a published structural model of *Tetrahymena* telomerase ([11], Fig. 6). AlphaFold3 predictions of RNA structures still have very low confidence in our experience, so with current technology, it is probably not worthwhile considering AI models of AtTR or the AtTR–AtLa1 complex. However, the overall structure of the *Tetrahymena* equivalent of TR is broadly similar to AtTR, in that it has two main ‘arms’ joined by a TWJ, one of which is a T/PK region and the other is the stem terminus element (STE) [11], equivalent to P4/5/6. Positioning of AtLa1/p65 domains on *Tetrahymena* TR is consistent with our *in vitro* mapping of the AtLa1–AtTR interface. Furthermore, there is clear space for AtTERT to bind within the main T/PK loop, which is unsurprising given the

high conservation between TERT structures from different organisms. It is, however, likely that the exact positioning of the xRRM differs in the At system or is otherwise dynamic, considering that the nearest key xRRM residues to flipped-out RNA bases in the overlaid At structure are F³³¹ and D³³³, both of which have no known impact on AtLa1–AtTR binding, whereas W³⁸⁷ does, and is situated a little far from RNA to interact (Fig. 6).

DUF3223 is a novel RNA-binding domain found in plants and ciliates

AtLa1 has one well-characterized protein binding partner, the DUF3223-containing protein AtDomino [16, 17]. Identified in this work is a semi-conserved SYD loop motif in AtLa1 that binds AtDomino, adjacent to the AtLa1 classical RRM domain. Experiments presented here also reveal that AtDomino binds RNA *in vitro* with nanomolar-range affinity, even when the positively charged C-terminus is removed, confirming that DUF3223 in AtDomino at least has RNA-binding activity as previously speculated [2, 39]. AtDomino has an affinity for AtTR, comparable to that of AtLa1, although we did not investigate a wide range of potential RNA substrates and cannot rule out interactions with other systems. So far, DUF3223 has been found only in plant-specific DCL proteins [39, 43], polymerases IV and V [41, 42], and ciliate genuine La proteins, such as Mlp1 [2, 40]. Solution NMR structural information is also available for a bacterial D3223 protein (PDB 2K0M). In polymerase V, DUF3223 (referred to as DeCL) is found in the largest subunit NRPE1 [41]. It binds the 3' exonuclease RRP6L1 and is essential for *in vivo* RNA-guided DNA methylation and gene silencing, but is dispensable for core activity *in vitro* [42]. As the processing of human TR precursor involves the participation of RRP6 [68], this raises the question of whether AtLa proteins have a role in the activity of plant-specific ribonucleases, or whether different DUF3223 domains carry structural specificity for selected roles.

AtDomino, like other DCL proteins, is essential for plant survival beyond embryogenesis [39, 43], and is proposed to have a role in ribosome biogenesis and cell division [39]. AtLa1 is also essential for plant survival beyond embryogenesis, suggesting that both proteins may be involved in the same essential pathway [38]. AtDomino has more protein–protein interactions with a variety of telomerase-related proteins, including AtTERT [17], suggesting a general role related to this system, perhaps in biogenesis of telomerase, a part of the active telomerase complex, or as a flexible protein–RNA chaperone.

The *Tetrahymena* genuine La protein Mlp1 (Supplementary Fig. S3G) has a unique role in variant ciliate tRNA processing [40]. This protein differs from classic La proteins in that it does not have a traditional La module; instead, it features only the La motif and a downstream DUF3223 [2, 40]. Sequence alignments with La and LARP7 proteins suggest an La motif adjacent to the xRRM domain is also present in Mlp1 in a region already known to bind RNA [40]. Curiously, this proposed domain structure of Mlp1 (La motif, xRRM, DUF3223) is similar to the complex of AtLa1 and AtDomino. It could be speculated that AtLa1 has evolved to perform either LARP7-like functions or Mlp1-like functions, depending on the binding of AtDomino, something that could be an interesting starting point for further studies.

Figure 6. Overlay of At structural predictions with *Tetrahymena* telomerase. Cryo-EM-derived structural model of *Tetrahymena* telomerase ([11], 8GAP) with p50 and Teb proteins omitted for clarity, proteins shown as transparent cartoons, and telomerase RNA backbone in black with flipped-out residues shown as sticks. AlphaFold2 [55] and AlphaFold3 [54] predictions of AtLa1 LaM (grey, 72 paired residues after pruning, RMSD = 1.182 Å), xRRM (red, 30 paired residues after pruning, RMSD = 1.038 Å), AtDomino (yellow, predicted complex with AtLa1 for comparison, no equivalent in 8GAP), and AtTERT (green, 273 paired residues after pruning, 1.322 Å) have been overlaid with 8GAP using the ChimeraX tool MatchMaker and visualized in ChimeraX [56]. Side panels show details of conserved xRRM residues (left) and the semi-conserved loop responsible for interactions between AtLa1 RRM and Domino.

Microscale thermophoresis is a sensitive technique for investigating protein–RNA interactions

Inspired by previous protein–RNA binding studies using oligonucleotides [69] or non-specific long RNA-binding protein domains [59], we used MST in this study to evaluate specific protein binding to structured non-coding RNA. One of our first observations was that we had biphasic changes in initial fluorescence and biphasic processes in some of our thermophoresis data proper. The classic thermophoresis data are easily rationalized in terms of a transition between two species with different mobility in solution, such as that observed in the 1:2 binding stoichiometry in the model system of arrestin binding to DNA aptamers, which is well-described by macroscopic or microscopic binding equations [70]. We also satisfied ourselves that initial fluorescence changes do not lead to artefactual differences in thermophoresis data as long as we stay within a range of fluorescence values already greater than the limits suggested by instrumental software (Fig. S2B). Although aggregation, visible as traces deviating randomly from a predictable curve, is present in the majority of the MST traces we recorded for protein–RNA binding studies, this is rarely present for the initial few seconds of experiment time, including the 1.5 s T-jump. Crucially, the initial fluorescence processes are absent if the local-viscosity-sensitive Cy5 label is moved from the 3′ terminus to the 5′ (Supplementary Fig. S2F), suggesting that they genuinely report on structural changes in the RNA molecule. Having ruled out obvious artefactual origins for our results, we then considered the intrinsic photochemical properties of our chosen fluorophore, Cy5. Cyanine dyes already have well-characterized protein-induced fluorescence intensity changes, which have been exploited for other techniques [52, 53]. Consistent with this, we were able to replicate our MST initial fluorescence measurements in a conventional fluorimeter (Supplementary Fig. S2C and D). The slow initial fluorescence change can therefore be described as a classic PIFE process [53], where protein binding to RNA changes the structure of

this molecule, leading to restriction of the Cy5 tag and therefore enhancement of fluorescence. Consistent with this, circular dichroism can be used to track global RNA structural changes (Supplementary Fig. S2C and E), suggesting that PIFE in this case reports on a process largely free of non-specific contributions, compared to the T-jump.

In some cases, Hill analysis (Fig. 1F and Supplementary Fig. S2C) may be more appropriate for the fast processes, which may have cooperative binding behaviour. For now, we have elected to keep the fitting of binding equations as simple as possible in our analysis to allow for easy comparison of values, at the risk of oversimplifying results.

The fast initial fluorescence process is perhaps a little more difficult to rationalize, presumably it is higher affinity than *bona fide* binding reported in thermophoresis, and represents a protein-induced fluorescence quenching (PIFQ, [52]).

PIFQ is described as arising from disruptions of fluorophore-labelled nucleic acid structure, thereby decreasing nucleic acid-induced fluorescent enhancement [52]. For our protein–RNA system, there is a lack of circular dichroism change over the range of this PIFQ, so such structural changes to RNA would be local to the Cy5 tag and not disrupt the overall A-form structure. This could be explained if, prior to binding (and therefore higher affinity by definition), pseudocontact between molecules leads to changes in flexible ssRNA conformation (such as the 3′ trailer) that do not affect paired dsRNA helical regions or the general overall molecular shape. Although observed for non-RRM binding events as well, this is broadly consistent with the predicted mechanism of RRM domain binding to RNA [64, 65], which features sequence-specific scanning of ssRNA (presumably responsible for PIFQ) prior to genuine binding based on sequence-related probability (giving rise to PIFE). Although we do not rely on the interpretation of initial fluorescence data for the system here, instead relying on the more typically interpreted T-jump, it is still possible that these additional processes (Supplementary Table S3) will

add an extra layer of information once more work has been done to unambiguously identify their origin.

Conclusions

MST is a user-friendly and highly flexible technique for determining the affinity of protein–RNA interactions in solution. The fluorophore used here is also sensitive to local structural changes, although the exact origin of the observed biphasic processes is still hypothetical. Comparing the *in vitro* TR binding properties of AtLa1 with LARP7 proteins, in particular with *Tetrahymena* p65, there are consistent similarities with the protein domains and RNA interfaces involved. Although AtLa1 TR binding data are *in vitro*, the presence of AtLa1 enhances AtTERT binding *in vivo* in a comparable way to the p65-initiated assembly of *Tetrahymena* telomerase. Based on these data, we hypothesize that a genuine La could fill one role of the otherwise-missing LARP7 in plants for the biogenesis of TR, in addition to its general role in RNA biogenesis. We cannot say yet whether La1 is part of the active telomerase complex, but our data so far are consistent with this possibility, pending further studies. Seemingly, of the few LARP7 proteins currently fully characterized there are examples of both those that are telomerase subunits, such as p65, p43, and Pof8, and those that are only involved in biogenesis, such as human LARP7. We also have evidence to support predictions that the DUF3223, present in the La-binding Domino protein, is a novel RNA-binding motif, together with its already characterized protein-binding capabilities. Currently, its exact role in the telomerase pathway, if any, is unknown, but we have identified a semi-conserved loop on plant La proteins that binds it. Both the conservation of the role of an La protein in telomerase and the presence of DUF3223 seem to be common traits of both plants and ciliates, hinting towards both arising from common ancestral RNA-processing systems.

Acknowledgements

L.J. is grateful to Jean-Luis Mergny and Václav Brázda (Institute of Biophysics CAS, Brno, Czech Republic) for advice on G4 characterization and Jaroslav Malina (Institute of Biophysics CAS, Brno, Czech Republic) for help with spectroscopy. We would also like to acknowledge Jiří Fajkus (Masaryk University Brno, Czech Republic) for fruitful discussion and support. The CIISB, Instruct-CZ Centre of Instruct-ERIC EU consortium, funded by MEYS CR infrastructure project LM2023042 and European Regional Development Fund Project ‘Innovation of Czech Infrastructure for Integrative Structural Biology’ (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/23_015/0008175), is gratefully acknowledged for financial support for measurements at the CF Biomolecular Interactions and Crystallography. Special thanks go to Tomáš Klumpler and Josef Houser (Central European Institute of Technology, Brno, Czech Republic) for their advice, support, and patience during L.J.’s use of the core facilities. Molecular structures were aligned and visualized using UCSF ChimeraX, developed by the Resource for Biocomputing, Visualization, and Informatics at the University of California, San Francisco, with support from National Institutes of Health and the Office of Cyber Infrastructure and Computational Biology, National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases.

Author contributions: Leon Jenner: Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Validation, Writing—original draft. Dzmitry Pruchkouski: Investigation, Methodology, Visualization. Writing—original draft. Barbora Štefanovic: Investigation, Validation, Visualization, Writing—original draft. Olga Nováková: Formal analysis, Resources. Monika Kubíčková: Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis. Petr Fajkus: Resources, Formal analysis. Marie Brázdová: Resources. Jan Paleček: Supervision, Resources, Writing—review & editing. Eva Sýkorová: Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing—original draft, review & editing.

Supplementary data

Supplementary data is available at NAR online.

Conflict of interest

None declared.

Funding

This work was supported by Czech Science Foundation [20-01331X to E.S.]. The work of J.P. and B.S. was funded by Czech Science Foundation grant GA25-15566S. The work of P.F. was supported from the project TowArds Next GENeration Crops, reg. no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004581 of the ERDF Programme Johannes Amos Comenius. Funding to pay the Open Access publication charges for this article was provided by Institutional funding.

Data availability

All data are incorporated into the article and its online supplementary material. SAXS data are deposited in the SASBDB under the codes SASDYP2 and SASDYQ2.

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